

Amphoterism of Hydrous Zirconium Oxide

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In this communication we have observed that acid or base exchange properties can be evoked in hydrous oxide ZrO_2 by precipitating it with varying amounts of alkali. The applicability of the Langmuir Adsorption Isotherm to the exchange processes involved has also been examined.

Kraus *et al.*¹ have observed that hydrous oxide ZrO_2 may exhibit either anion exchange or cation exchange properties depending on the acidity of the solutions. While studying the uptake of some anions and cations by hydrous oxide ZrO_2 , Amphlett *et al.*² established that the process involves ion exchange resulting either in an increase or a decrease in the pH of the systems. Singh *et al.*³ have observed that the penetration of SO_4^{-2} ions is greater than that of NO_3^- ions in this hydrous oxide. It has been observed in these laboratories that acid or base exchange characteristics of various metal hydroxides can be altered by controlling the amount of alkali used for the purpose of precipitation⁴⁻⁵. The present investigations lead to the conclusion that the various systems studied here can be successfully represented by the Langmuir equation.

$$x/m = \alpha\beta c/(1+\alpha c),$$

where

$$x/m = \text{adsorption per gram of the adsorbent,}$$

$$c = \text{equilibrium concentration,}$$

and

$$\alpha, \beta = \text{Langmuir's constants.}$$

EXPERIMENTAL

Three different samples (A, B, and C) of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 were precipitated at 30° by a rapid addition of 10% deficient, equivalent, and 10% excess amounts of 0.5882M NaOH solution to a fixed volume of a well-stirred 0.5876M aqueous solution of $Zr(NO_3)_4$. The gelatinous precipitate of hydrous oxide was slurried with re-distilled CO_2 -free water several times until completely free from salt, alkali, and ions (wherever present). The purified samples were homogenised on a Microid flask shaker and separately estimated for their zirconia content.

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Adsorption studies were carried out by allowing varying quantities of standard electrolyte solutions to equilibrate with 0.05 gm zirconia (ZrO_2) in several graduated flasks maintained at 30° for an overnight. The total volume of the equilibrating systems was maintained constant at 50 ml. The equilibrium concentrations of different electrolytes in the supernatant liquid were determined by usual methods.

The initial pH of the suspensions of the samples A, B and C of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 were found to be 8.75, 8.60 and 8.60, respectively. Therefore, to avoid the effect of pH -discrepancies on the exchange capacity of the various samples of the hydrous oxide 5 ml of buffer (pH 8.60; borax + boric acid) solution, which was found to be adequate to maintain the desired pH , was added to each flask. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adsorption of ions-dichromate from $K_2Cr_2O_7$, oxalate from $H_2C_2O_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ and cupric from $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ —on the surface of the samples A, B and C of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 was studied. Representative analytical data for the sample A are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Adsorption of $Cr_2O_7^{-2}$, $C_2O_4^{-2}$ and Cu^{+2} ions by hydrous oxide ZrO_2

(Sample A)

Ion	Initial Conc. (gm.Ms $\times 10^6$)	Equilibrium conc. (c) (gm.Ms $\times 10^6$)	Amount adsorbed (gm.Ms $\times 10^6$)	Adsorption (x/m) (gm.Ms $\times 10^5$)
Dichromate	1000	526	474	948
	1500	381	619	1238
	2000	1319	681	1362
	3000	2167	833	1666
	4000	3085	915	1830
Oxalate	1000	18	982	1964
	2000	70	1930	3860
	3000	524	2476	4952
	4000	1416	2584	5168
	5000	2575	2425	4850
Cupric	1000	71	929	1858
	2000	647	1353	2706
	3000	1484	1516	3032
	4000	2342	1658	3316
	5000	3297	1703	3406

It is evident from the plots (Figs. 1-3) of c against $c/(x/m)$ that the Langmuir's linear relationship

$$c/(x/m) = \frac{1}{\alpha\beta} + \frac{c}{\beta}$$

holds good for the systems—dichromate, oxalate and cupric ions—in contact with the sample A of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 . Similar straight lines (plots not given here) are obtained for the samples B and C. On measuring the slopes and intercepts of the straight lines (Figs. 1-3),

Fig. 1-3.

the equations obtained for the three different ions in equilibrium with hydrous oxide ZrO_2 are :

Dichromate	$c/(x/m)$	$gm^{-1} = 44.21c + 0.0330$
Oxalate	$c/(x/m)$	$gm^{-1} = 20.30c + 0.0004$
Cupric	$c/(x/m)$	$gm^{-1} = 29.14c + 0.0024$

The values of Langmuir's constants α and β , calculated from the above equations, are reported in the following table.

TABLE II

Values of Langmuir's constants α and β for the systems—dichromate, oxalate, and cupric ions in contact with hydrous oxide ZrO_2 —at equilibrium

Ion	$\alpha\beta$	α	β
Dichromate	0.30×10^2	13.40×10^2	2.26×10^{-2}
Oxalate	25.00×10^2	50.77×10^3	4.92×10^{-2}
Cupric	4.16×10^2	12.14×10^3	3.43×10^{-2}

In the Langmuir equation, since α is a coefficient of the equilibrium concentration (c), high magnitudes of the former would necessarily mean a considerable decrease in the values of the latter during exchange and consequently greater adsorption. It is evident from above

table that the values of α are fairly large in comparison to β -values, the latter being proportional to total surface area of the adsorbent, and hence its low values meaning availability of less surface for exchange. Therefore, fairly large exchange capacity of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 , in spite of the latter offering less available surface is attributed to the following two possibilities :

(1) Surface area of the adsorbent available for chemical interaction with the adsorbate (chemisorption) is sufficiently high whereas the same is quite low for physical adsorption.

(2) Sporadic adsorption takes place at the active spots on the surface of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 with high efficiency for exchange.

The experimental data show that the exchange capacities of the various samples of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 for the anions dichromate and oxalate follow the order

$$A > B > C$$

whereas for the cation (cupric) the exchange capacities of these samples follow just the reverse order, i.e.,

$$C > B > A$$

This difference arises due to amphotericism of hydrous oxide ZrO_2 which is precipitated by the interaction of zirconium (IV) and hydroxyl ions, according to the scheme

Equation (1) shows the basic nature of the hydrous oxide explaining greater exchange of anions by the precipitate (A). Furthermore, the liberation of a proton from the positively charged material $Zr(OH)_3^+$ is responsible for evoking acidic characteristic of the hydrous oxide leading to its greater exchange capacity for the cations (C). This is facilitated by increasing the amount of alkali for the purpose of precipitation. Mutual interaction between acidic and basic properties results in the liberation of H_2O (3).

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